

FINAL REPORT

1 General Information

- DFG reference number: SCHO 1562/7-1.
- Project number: 443179833.
- Project title: Bembel: The Boundary Element Based Engineering Library.
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- Name(s) of the co-applicants: None.
- Name(s) of the cooperation partners: Jürgen Dölz, University of Bonn.
- Reporting period (entire funding period): 2022-01-01 to 2023-12-31

2 Summary

The Bembel research project addresses the challenge of balancing the advancement of research with the development of maintainable code. Often, developers implement their research in their own branches, which diverge significantly from the main codebase, leading to inconsistencies and integration difficulties. Without clear rules and guidelines, the codebase can become disorganized and difficult to manage, hindering further development.

The project goals were achieved through two initiatives. First, the maintainability of Bembel was improved by implementing software engineering principles. Comprehensive software testing was incorporated for quality assurance, workflows were automated through continuous integration, and refactoring improved code quality. Coding principles were discussed in developer workshops, agreed upon and written down in the documentation.

On the other hand, Bembel's functional capabilities were extended to make it more attractive for users. This included the integration of a Computer Aided Design (CAD) software interface and the introduction of a circuit-oriented Partial Element Equivalent Circuit (PEEC) method. With these improvements, new classes of problems can now be solved with Bembel.

To demonstrate the applicability of Bembel, the software was used to solve two new challenging practical problems.

Zusammenfassung

Das Bembel-Forschungsprojekt befasst sich mit der Herausforderung, ein Gleichgewicht zwischen dem Vorantreiben der Forschung und der Entwicklung von wartbarem Code herzustellen. Oftmals implementieren Entwickler*innen ihre Forschungsarbeiten in eigenen Zweigen, die erheblich von der Hauptcodebasis abweichen, was zu Inkonsistenzen und Integrationsschwierigkeiten führt. Ohne klare Regeln und Richtlinien kann die Codebasis unübersichtlich und schwer zu warten werden, was die weitere Entwicklung behindert.

Die Projektziele wurden durch zwei Initiativen erreicht. Erstens wurde die Wartbarkeit von Bembel durch die Anwendung von Software-Engineering-Prinzipien verbessert. Zur Qualitätssicherung wurden umfassende Softwaretests eingeführt, Arbeitsabläufe durch kontinuierliche Integration automatisiert und die Codequalität durch Refactoring verbessert. Entwicklungsprinzipien wurden in Entwickler-Workshops diskutiert, verabschiedet und in der Dokumentation niedergeschrieben.

Andererseits wurden die funktionalen Möglichkeiten von Bembel erweitert, um es für Benutzer*innen attraktiver zu machen. Dazu gehörten die Integration einer Computer Aided Design (CAD)-Software-Schnittstelle und die Einführung der schaltungsorientierten Partial Element Equivalent Circuit (PEEC)-Methode. Mit diesen Verbesserungen können nun neue Klassen von Problemen mit Bembel gelöst werden.

Um die Anwendbarkeit von Bembel zu demonstrieren, wurde die Software zur Lösung zweier neuer anspruchsvoller Probleme aus Praxis eingesetzt.

3 Progress Report

Bembel's initial development was based on routines and data structures designed almost twenty years ago which were original only meant to solve simple Laplace problems. The development of increasingly complex algorithms around these data structures has led to an inflexible architecture that hampered the further development of the software. For each new problem, the code was copied and modified in a few places. Each developer had their own copy of the code, i.e. their own repository, where they developed new features and fixed bugs. Without coding guidelines and workflows, this led to a growing amount of merge conflicts and increased technical debt. Furthermore, to validate the code, there were only a few unit tests for low-level routines. Some examples that tested the implementation as a whole needed to be evaluated by hand. Code reviews were carried out manually.

The project goals were achieved through two initiatives. On the one hand, software engineering processes have been implemented that enable the sustainable development of Bembel as a collaborative project with currently six active researchers. This improves the usability and provides the basis for

implementing new features on the other hand.

The original proposal formulated several **objectives** which are repeated in the following (*text in italic*) with their corresponding level of implementation.

Source repository *The source repository is available on Github. We follow the usual design, i.e., master, stable and developer (feature) branches. Whereas the master branch will contain the current release, the stable branch will feature additional features which have passed the internal code review as outlined below and which were considered to be fully working and tested. Thus, the stable branch collects all features suitable to be merged into the master branch. The two branches will be protected accordingly. The developer branches (or forks) will be used for the development of entirely new features. The continuous integration will be accomplished by Circleci.*

Achieved. The git branching model with master, release and feature branches is established and documented in the guidelines. Continuous integration is accomplished with Github actions which allow running the tests in user repositories without prior setup.

Programming languages *The high-level routines of Bembel are written in C++, whereas a large portion of the core routines are written in legacy C code which is parallelized by OpenMP. The legacy C routines are hindering the further development and usability of the code and will be replaced by C++ routines which are parallelized by OpenMP. Template based programming will be used to allow for more flexibility in the code base and sustainable future development.*

Achieved. After refactoring all legacy C code was ported to C++. Furthermore, template based programming is established. The flexibility is demonstrated by a number of new problem classes which can be solved by Bembel.

Coding standards *We follow the Google C++ style guide.*

Achieved. The code is now checked with the cpplint (static code checker for C++) automatically, see Table 1.

Build system *We use Cmake as a build system and will continue to do so.*

Achieved. The Cmake build system has been extended to support also Windows systems.

Testing *Currently, only a part of the low-level routines is covered by unit tests and whereas high-level routines are covered by example programs which are run manually. To increase the test coverage of our library, we will write automated unit tests for all low-level routines. We will also develop automated test cases for high-level routines wherever this is possible.*

Achieved. The unit test suite has been extended to cover all low-level routines and most of the high-level routines. Furthermore, the tests are automated including checks of the mathematical correctness. A code coverage report is deployed automatically when merging pull-requests, see Table 1.

Bug tracking *Bugs are currently shared between developers via email. We will switch to the issue tracker of Github to allow for input from external users.*

Achieved. Bugs are now consequently tracked with Github issues (20 issues have been closed, 10 are currently open, none of them critical).

Debugging and profiling tools *We currently use Valgrind to detect memory errors, Helgrind to detect memory races and GDB for debugging and stepping through code. We will complement these tools with cpplint.py from Google to check (partially) whether our coding standards are fulfilled, Cppcheck for a static code analysis, and Gcov to analyze the test coverage of the code.*

Achieved. A static code analysis is carried out with cpplint on every push. A code coverage reported is deployed automatically when merging pull-requests, see Table 1. The tools Valgrind, Helgrind and GDB are not run automatically but are used manually by the developers.

Code reviews *Currently, all developers have write access to the master branch and code reviews are not common practice. We will establish four eye reviews based on merge requests for all merges into the stable branch, which is protected accordingly. For the review we will define a detailed protocol [...].*

Achieved. The master branch is protected and a code review is necessary for merging a pull-request. Running tests is automated by the continuous integration on Github Actions. This includes a static code analysis with the cpplint which also checks the compliance with the Google coding style guide, see Table 1.

Release engineering *At the present stage we do not yet have an established release engineering process. We plan to make an annual release which will always be available on the master branch of the Github repository. The annual release will be shortly after the developer and user meetings (see below) and will consist of merging the stable branch into the master branch. As indicated above, the stable branch is protected by a review procedure. The merge of the stable branch into the master branch will be addressed in the developer meeting.*

Achieved. Version 1.1 is released and achieved on Zenodo [1].

Post mortems *In case of serious failure of development processes or structural technical problems, the search for possible solutions will be performed in close contact with the advisory board.*

Indicator	Measurement tool	Before	Targeted	Achieved
Test coverage of functions	Gcov	77%	>90%	99%
Test coverage of lines	Gcov	54%	>90%	94%
Documentation coverage	Doxygen	593 warnings	0 warnings	565 warning
Manual Pages	Doxygen	-	-	5
Coding style fulfilled	cppLint.py	1337 warnings	0 warnings	0 warnings
Contributors on Github	Github	2	6	7
Forks on Github	Github	8	20	21
Stars on Github	Github	13	40	51
Issues on Github	Github	-	-	10 (+20 closed)
Citations of [2]	Google Scholar	2	15	31

Table 1: Indicator, intended measurement tool, current status (as of April 7, 2026) and target towards the end of the project to evaluate the progress of the software development throughout the project.

Achieved. However, measure was not yet required.

Developer meetings *We plan to have annual developer meetings as an appendix to the annual user workshops (see below). These meetings will take place before the annual release and will be used to discuss larger feature developments for the next year and to inform about the development of smaller features from the last year.*

Achieved. Developer workshops and meetings were carried out. In particular as part of the first workshop, the workflow was aligned. This includes an agreement on common development principles and coding guidelines.

Feature development *Feature development itself will take place within the developer branches or within forked repositories. The developed features must pass the code review protocol before they can be merged into the stable branch.*

Achieved. This process is established and well documented.

Hotfixes *Should a critical bug be reported on the issue tracker of Github, we will announce the next steps within one week. This will happen regardless of whether the bug was reported by the developers or by a user. A hotfix must pass the the code review protocol as outlined above and a test case covering that specific failure must be created.*

Achieved. A few necessary hotfixes have been merged successfully.

Documentation *Currently, a Doxygen file is provided with the code base which the user can run on his or her system. A rudimentary documentation of the high-level routines and example programs are available. We will complete the missing Doxygen documentation and improve and extend the documentation of the high-level routines and examples. Missing documentation will*

be detected from the output of Doxygen and the final documentation will be provided on Github pages. The documentation will be complemented by additional academic examples from classroom teaching (see below) and more advanced examples from research collaborations. The technical report [2] shall serve as a starting point.

Mostly Achieved. The documentation has been significantly extended, in particular tutorials have been included as Doxygen manual pages, see Table 1. However, the targeted 0 warnings in the documentation coverage turned out to be too optimistic, considering that even undocumented variables in ('private') core structs and classes are causing warnings.

Feature requests and bug reports *We will encourage users to use the issue tracker of Github to submit feature requests and bug reports. If such requests are directed to one of the developers via email, the corresponding developer will make these requests and reports available on the public issue tracker.*

Achieved. The Github issues tracker is consequently used (20 issues have been closed, 10 are currently open, none of them critical).

User workshops *In junction with the annual developer meeting we will hold an annual user workshop. The workshops aim at contributions from researchers using Bembel within their research projects as well as to presentations from researchers exploring the possibility to use Bembel in their future research. We will also conduct user surveys to assess missing features and wishes.*

Not yet on larger scale. However, individual trainings have been offered to first time users, e.g. with groups at TU Graz and ETH Zürich. Until now, working with individual Bembel users involves close support from the developers.

Classroom teaching *The high-level C++ classes of Bembel are designed for simple usage such that a classroom usage of the library as a black-box tool is feasible. We aim at using Bembel for the computation of scattered acoustic and electromagnetic fields in Bachelor and Master courses at TU Darmstadt. In particular, a dedicated lecture on isogeometric analysis is scheduled for summer term 2020. For the particular requirements of classroom teaching we will provide comprehensive example programs which are complemented by tutorials, e.g. based on jupyter-notebooks.*

Achieved. Bembel is discussed in the lecture 'Schnelle Randelementmethoden im Ingenieurwesen' given by Dr. Felix Wolf. with a compulsory exercise class taught by Maximilian Nolte. Furthermore, three students under the supervision of Prof. Jürgen Dölz use Bembel via a Python interface.

Software description *We also will provide examples for more challenging problems (e.g. antennas, resonators or machines). [...]*

Achieved. For example the balun model in [3] demonstrates a challenging problem from the field of electromagnetic compatibility.

Marketing *The developers are part of a scientific community which is rich on potential users (see also the paragraph on target purpose). Therefore, each conference offers the possibility to gain new users. [...]*

Achieved. For example, the talks [4–7] and posters [8, 9] were used to introduce Bembel to a broader audience. A tutorial was given within the 2022 BEM summer school organized by Olaf Steinbach and Martin Schanz from TU Graz.

In the following the **work programme** from the proposal is repeated (*text in italic*) with its corresponding level of implementation.

Planned redesign *The current data structures in legacy C will be redesigned and adapted to the state of the art. For this purpose template-based C++ programming shall be used (e.g. concerning complex/real arithmetic). [...]*

Done. See above.

Interoperability *Simplified interoperability over API with established isogeometric software packages [...]*

Done. Routines for importing and exporting GeoPDEs file format have been implemented.

Caldéron Projector *Sustainable integration of the Caldéron projector for Laplace, Helmholtz and electric wave equation. The necessary quadrature routines are already available and tested, but not yet integrated into the library due to the hindrances of the existing legacy C data structures. This will be funded by the remaining budget from the already granted projects SCHO 1562/3-1 and KU 1553/4-1.*

Deviation from the original plan. Research on the Caldéron projector was given up in SCHO 1562/3-1 and KU 1553/4-1. Therefore, instead of implementing a more sophisticated iterative solver within Bembel, another approach was followed: reformulating Maxwell's equations in terms of potentials as in the PEEC (Partial Element Equivalent Circuit) method allows to export the equations as a circuit netlist and to use the specialised solvers from Spice-like circuit simulation tools. This also aids the integration of Bembel in complex simulation workflows. Both, an electrostatic and full-wave solver have been implemented. They are tested by academic examples and applied to an involved application example with severe curvature, see [3, 10].

Additional features *such as Gram's matrices and more general fundamental solutions that allow the library to be used for more general technical problems will also be funded from the remaining budget.*

Done. These features have been implemented to the code base. One example for more general fundamental solutions is published in [11].

CAD data formats *Import and export of additional CAD data formats. Currently only the import of untrimmed (NURBS) geometries in the file format of the Octave NURBS package is supported. In a first step, the import and export of geometry files in IGES format should be supported.*

Done. IGES import and export is implemented.

More data formats *Improved export of geometries and data into VTU-files for the visualization within Paraview. In the future also the import of trimmed geometries shall be supported.*

Work in progress. However, a cooperation with Prof. Benjamin Marussig, TU Graz has been initiated to work on advanced CAD topics with STEP which can handle trimmed surfaces.

Automated testing and continuous integration *The implementation of the redesign is supported by continuous integration and automated testing as outlined above.*

Done. The test suite is extended and run automatically.

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4 Published Project Results

4.1 Publications with scientific quality assurance

- [10] R. Torchio, M. Nolte, S. Schöps, and A. E. Ruehli. “A Spline-based Partial Element Equivalent Circuit Method for Electrostatics”. In: *IEEE Transactions on Dielectrics and Electrical Insulation* 30.2 (2023). DOI: 10.1109/TDEI.2022.3224890. arXiv: 2207.13697

4.2 Other publications and published results

- [3] M. Nolte, R. Torchio, S. Schöps, J. Dölz, F. Wolf, and A. E. Ruehli. *A Low-Frequency-Stable Higher-Order Spline-Based Integral Equation Method*. Preprint. Cornell University, 2024. arXiv: 2401.10735
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4.3 Patents (applied for and granted)

None.

5 Further information on the project, qualifications and outlook

Description of the progress. All relevant project goals were achieved, see the detailed discussions above. The only deviation from the original plan concerns the implementation of the Caldéron projector, which was not carried out because the expected theoretical results were not available. Instead, thanks to a collaboration with Riccardo Torchio (Department of Industrial Engineering, Università degli Studi di Padova, Italy) and Albert E. Ruehli (EMC Laboratory, Missouri University of Science and Technology, Rolla, MO USA), an isogeometric variant of the Partial Element Equivalent Circuit (PEEC) method was implemented. This turned out to be easy thanks to the new clean data structures provided by this project. The most time-consuming aspect was the verification ('solving the equations right' according to [12]) of industrially relevant problems, e.g. with respect to results from commercial software (e.g. CST and FEKO). Although the geometric data were given exactly in the form of splines, import routines, meshing, differences in the implementation of methods (e.g. FEM and BEM) and boundary conditions caused deviations that had to be identified and worked around. Finally, a multi-tapered coaxial balun was simulated and compared with CST and FEKO. The results are very satisfactory, Bembel can directly import the CAD data, obtains results much faster than other tools and the agreement with reference results is excellent. We conclude that Bembel has reached a higher Technology Readiness Level (TRL), i.e. from TRL-3 ('characteristic proof of concept') to TRL-4 ('laboratory validation').

Follow-up studies. In the reporting period, several publications and theses have been completed which are using Bembel for their numerical studies, [3, 10, 11, 13–21]. Furthermore, the projects C03 ('Advanced Isogeometric Framework for the Analysis of Electric Drives') and C05 ('Noise and Vibration of Electric Drives: Space-Time Boundary Element Formulations') within the SFB TRR-361 CREATOR are using Bembel as a starting point for their implementations.